

Proton-Ligand Stability Constants of Serinehydroxamic Acid and Threoninehydroxamic Acid in Mixed Aqueous Solvents

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The biological importance of hydroxamic and aminohydroxamic acids is beyond any doubt¹. The inhibitory activity of aminohydroxamic acids on metalloproteinases has been reported². Serinehydroxamate inhibited protein synthesis in *Escherichia coli* by competitively inhibiting acryl t-RNA synthetase³. Threoninehydroxamate is an effective inhibitor of *Aeromonas proteolytic* aminopeptidases⁴. Mixed aqueous organic solvents provide a range of media where dielectric constant varies and proton-solvent interactions also change. The present work has been carried out on the determination of proton-ligand stability constants of serinehydroxamic acid and threoninehydroxamic acid in various mixed aqueous solvents.

Results and Discussion

The potentiometric titration curves of protonated serinehydroxamic acid (SerHA) are shown in Fig. 1 for only methanol-water system at 0.24 mole fraction of organic solvent. All other titration curves were of similar nature. For each ligand, two proton-ligand stability constants $\log K_1^{H_1}$ and $\log K_2^{H_2}$ were determined in various aqueous organic mixtures. Values of $\bar{n}_A$ were calculated in the pH range 5–11 by Irving-Rossotti method⁵. The proton-ligand stability constants were calculated from proton-ligand formation curves $\bar{n}_A$ versus pH, using least-square method⁵. Brown and Roche⁶ have reported $\log K_1^{H_1}$ 8.96 and $\log K_2^{H_2}$ 6.79 corresponding to the protonation of NH_2 group and NHO^- group respectively, in aqueous medium at 25° for serinehydroxamic acid and the present values in aqueous medium (Table 1) are in close agreement with the above reported values for SerHA and no data is available for proton-ligand stability constants of threoninehydroxamic acid (ThrHA) in aqueous medium.

Considering the effect of dielectric constant (ϵ) at constant mole fraction 0.24 of organic solvent on log

$K_1^{H_1}$ and $\log K_2^{H_2}$ values in methanol-water, ethanol-water, isopropanol-water and dioxan-water mixtures at constant ionic strength of 0.2M NaCl (Table 1), the plots of $\log K_1^{H_1}$ vs $1/\epsilon$ (curves not shown) showed that $\log K_1^{H_1}$ increases with increase in $1/\epsilon$ for each ligand. However, the rate of increase was comparatively

Fig 1 Titration curves for serinehydroxamic acid (SerHA) in methanol-water at 0.24 mole fraction of organic solvent and at 0.2M ionic strength (X) acid only and (O) Acid + SerHA

greater at the initial stage but gradually became less afterwards with both the ligands. In case of both SerHA and ThrHA, $\log K_2^H$ values increased in each aquo-organic mixture at constant mole fraction of 0.24 compared to aqueous medium only. However, the $\log K_2^H$ values were not much different in case of SerHA in different aquo-organic mixtures. In case of ThrHA, $\log K_2^H$ gradually increased with increase in $1/\epsilon$. At mole fraction of 0.24 of organic solvent, structuredness of water⁷ crossed the maximum value for all the other media. Therefore, approximately upto 0.24 mole fraction water has its usual acidity and ionic components of the proton-ligand bond responses to the change in $1/\epsilon$.

TABLE I—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SERINYLHYDROXAMIC ACID (SERHA) AND THREONINEHYDROXAMIC ACID (THRHA) IN AQUEOUS AND AQUEO-ORGANIC MIXTURES*

Temp = 25°, Ionic strength = 0.2M (NaCl)

Solvent composition % (v/v)	Mole fraction of organic solvent	1/ε	log K_1^H		log K_2^H	
			SerHa	ThrHa	SerHA	ThrHA
Aqueous	0.0	0.013 0	9.03	8.89	6.81	6.92
Methanol-water	0.24	0.016 7	9.30	9.29	6.92	7.04
Ethanol-water	0.24	0.019 8	9.34	9.32	6.90	7.00
Isopropanol-water	0.24	0.025 4	9.47	9.44	6.95	7.10
Dioxan-water	0.24	0.039 9	9.81	9.90	6.90	7.14
Dioxan-water (20.0)	0.050	0.016 5	9.30	9.08	6.91	6.92
Dioxan-water (40.0)	0.123	0.023 4	9.63	9.50	6.99	7.13
Dioxan-water (50.0)	0.174	0.029 3	9.57	9.49	6.88	7.07

*Standard deviations of values are ± 0.02 log units.

The proton-ligand stability constant measurements were repeated separately in 20, 40 and 50% (v/v) dioxan concentration in dioxan-water mixtures. Here $\log K_1^H$ for SerHA and ThrHA increased with $1/\epsilon$ upto 40% dioxan concentration. Similar response was obtained in case of $\log K_2^H$ value for SerHA but only at 40% (v/v) dioxane concentration in case of ThrHA. Both $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ values either decreased or remained unaltered at 50% dioxan concentration in dioxan-water mixture. At 50–60% dioxan concentration, structuredness of water gradually decreased and water became less acidic or more basic which may lower $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$. Also in the presence of large

organic solvent concentration, the proton solvation of organic solvent also lower $\log K^H$ values⁷.

Experimental

DL-Serinehydroxamate(2-amino-N,3-dihydroxypropanamide) and DL-threoninehydroxamate(2-amino-N,3-dihydroxybutanamide) (Sigma) were used. The ligand solutions were prepared in double-distilled water and their purity was checked by potentiometric titrations. NaCl (AnalaR) was used to maintain the constant ionic strength. NaOH (0.1 N) was prepared in carbonate-free distilled water and standardised.

The pH-titration technique of Irving and Rossotti⁵ was used to determine proton-ligand stability constants and the pH values in aquo-organic mixtures were corrected using the method of Van Uitert and Haas⁸. The following mixtures were prepared in aqueous medium at ionic strength of 0.2 M and titrated against 0.1 N NaOH potentiometrically: (i) 1 ml of 0.1N HCl + 2 ml of 2M NaCl + 17 ml of H₂O, (ii) 1 ml of 0.1N HCl + 2 ml of 2M NaCl + 2 ml of 0.017 M ligand + 15 ml water. The above titrations were also performed in (a) 20, 40 and 50% (v/v) dioxane-water media and (b) at constant mole fraction 0.24 of organic solvent in methanol-water (42.5 : 57.5%, v/v), ethanol-water (51.8 : 48.2%, v/v), isopropanol-water (58.6 : 41.4%, v/v) and dioxane-water (61.2 : 38.8%, v/v) mixtures at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ and ionic strength of 0.2M.

A ECIL 5652 pH meter with glass and calomel electrode assembly was used for pH measurements to an accuracy of ± 0.01 pH unit. The values of dielectric constant for the solvent composition were either obtained or calculated from the data available in literature⁹.

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